

STUDIES IN THE CHEMISTRY OF TELLURIUM. PART II.
THE ELECTRODIC BEHAVIOUR OF TELLURIUM IN
BUFFER SOLUTIONS OF VARYING pH

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Tellurium electrodes, prepared from the powdered metal or by electrodeposition and then subjected to the alternate action of hydrogen and high vacuum or prepared by sublimation in vacuum, set up potentials in oxygen-free buffer solutions, which coincide with the thermodynamic potentials of the Te/TeO_2 system. They differ thus from the potentials set by the massive electrodes or electrodes prepared by electrodeposition in aerated solutions which are more positive by ~ 160 mv. This excess potential corresponds to 2/15 of the electrode surface being covered with oxygen doublets.

In a previous investigation two of us studied the applicability of tellurium as indicator electrode in acid-base titrations (Tourky, Issa and Awad, *Chim. Anal.*, 1955, 37, 367). For this purpose the behaviour of tellurium electrodes, prepared either from tellurium rods or by electrodeposition, was investigated in buffer solutions of pH 1-12. Tellurium rods or tellurium electrodes, prepared by electrodeposition from weakly acid solutions of TeO_2 ($pH \sim 3$), showed a pH -potential relationship consisting of two linear portions covering the pH ranges 1-5 and 7-12. Electrodes prepared by electrodeposition from fairly acid solutions (2N-HCl) showed, on the other hand, a linear plot within the pH range 3-11. Extrapolation of the linear portions to $pH = 0$ yielded in case of the former electrodes E'_0 values which within the pH range 1-5 amount to 0.53 volt, and within the pH range 7-12 to 0.69 volt. The E'_0 values, obtained by tellurium electrodes deposited from fairly acid solutions, approached the higher E'_0 value, i.e. 0.69 volt.

In this investigation it is aimed to throw some light on the electrode mechanism from a study of the behaviour of the tellurium electrode out of contact with atmospheric oxygen and from its behaviour on cathodic and anodic polarisation.

EXPERIMENTAL

The electrodes studied were obtained from (a) the massive or the powdered metal, (b) by electrodeposition and (c) by sublimation.

(A). The massive tellurium electrodes were prepared by the process described previously by Khalifa and Issa (this *Journal*, 1957, 35, 88) and shown in Fig 1 a.

(B) *Powdered electrodes*.—The metal powder was obtained by reducing an acid solution of tellurium dioxide with sulphur dioxide. The powder was placed in a small glass cup surrounding platinum wires sealed to glass tubings that could be filled with mercury for maintaining the electrical contact.

(C). Electrodes prepared by sublimation of powdered tellurium, after being subjected to the reducing action of hydrogen and high vacuum at 400° .

Cells and Apparatus.—Measurements in air were carried out in an electrode vessel similar to that previously given (Issa *et al.*, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1955, 74, 1506). The electrode vessel (c) shown in Fig. 1 is used to carry out measurements while bubbling either purified nitrogen or hydrogen through the solution. The vessel (e, Fig. 1) is designed for measuring the potentials of tellurium electrodes out of contact with atmospheric oxygen, and after subjecting them to the alternate action of hydrogen and high vacuum between 200° and 400°. Electrodes subjected to the above treatment were either prepared by electrodeposition or by sublimation.

FIG. 1
Electrode jackets and cells

Electrodeposited electrodes were heated in vacuum at 300° and in hydrogen at 400°. This treatment was followed on account of the tendency of tellurium to volatilise in vacuum at about 320° (Latimer "Oxidation Potentials", Prentice-Hall, N.Y., 1953, p. 86).

After repeating this process twice, the electrode jacket (b, Fig. 1) was evacuated, left to cool and then separated from the vacuum system by sealing at a narrow constriction. By the aid of a breaking device in the electrode vessel (e, Fig. 1) containing the air-free buffer, the electrode jacket could be completely filled with the solution.

Electrodes prepared by sublimation were obtained by subjecting the powdered metal to the reducing action of hydrogen at 400°, followed by high vacuum at 320°. The metal sublimed and deposited on a platinum wire sealed inside the electrode jacket (d, Fig. 1). Electrical contact in all cases was maintained through mercury and copper wires.

Behaviour of Tellurium Electrodes prepared by Electrodeposition

(a) *In Air*.—Curves a and b (Fig. 2) represent the potential- p_{H_2} plots three hours after immersion for tellurium electrodes prepared from neutral and alkaline tellurate solutions respectively on a platinum substrate. These curves represent a linear relation between p_{H_2} and potential within the p_{H_2} range 2-12 with the respective slopes, 67 and 58. By extrapolation to zero p_{H_2} , E_0^{Te} values amounting to 650 and 680 mV successively were obtained.

FIG. 2

Electrodeposited electrodes (a) from neutral cd_2 from alkaline (c) hydrogen bubbling (d) H_2 bubbling

FIG. 3

(a) massicot CH_2 (b) Te/TeO_2 (c) massicot after anodic treatment (d) massicot after cathodic treatment.

FIG. 4

Potential- pH relation for tellurium electrodes pretreated with hydrogen.

Curves c and d in Fig 2. show the behaviour of electrodeposited electrodes in solutions originally freed from dissolved oxygen by bubbling purified nitrogen or hydrogen through the solution for a period of 30 minutes while the electrodes were immersed in the solution. Both curves are linear and possess slopes of 59 mv. They differ from the curves obtained in aerated solutions in that the potentials set in the latter case are more positive. The potentials initially set in presence of hydrogen are even less positive than those of the Te/TeO₂ system. Thus, by extrapolation to zero p_{H_2} , E' values amounting to 600 and 400 mv are obtained in case of nitrogen and hydrogen respectively. In both cases the potentials tend to more positive values with time till they reach after prolonged immersion the values obtained in air.

(b) *Out of Contact with Air.*—Curve d in Fig. 4 represents the behaviour of the electrodeposited electrodes after subjecting them to the alternate action of hydrogen and high vacuum. The potentials which remain practically constant throughout a period of 24 hours lie on a straight line which coincides with the theoretical ones for the Te/TeO₂ system.

Behaviour of Powdered Electrodes

(a) *In Air.*—Curve b in Fig. 4 shows the behaviour of electrodes prepared from the powdered metal. From the results obtained in air it was found that within the p_{H_2} range 1-5, the potentials set 3 hours after immersion lie in the region of the Te/TeO₂ system. Above this p_{H_2} range the potentials are somewhat more positive than the corresponding thermodynamic values but tend to drift with time to less positive potentials till they approach after 24 hours those of the Te/TeO₂ system.

(b) *Out of Contact with Air.*—Powdered electrodes, after being subjected to the alternate action of hydrogen and high vacuum set potentials which, as may be seen from curves a and b in Fig. 4, coincide within the p_{H_2} range 1-10 with the thermodynamic values.

Behaviour of Sublimed Electrodes

Curve c in Fig 4 represents the behaviour of tellurium electrodes prepared by sublimation. These electrodes like those subjected to the alternate action of hydrogen and high vacuum set potentials which lie in the region of the thermodynamic values.

Behaviour of Stick Tellurium Electrodes after Cathodic and Anodic Treatment

Curves d and c in Fig. 3 represent the variation of potentials with p_{H_2} , set by the massive electrodes after being subjected to cathodic and anodic polarisation at 4×10^{-5} amps/cm². In both cases the potentials lie on almost straight lines and yield on extrapolation to $p_{\text{H}_2} = 0$, E' values amounting to 400 and 650 mv in case of cathodically and anodically treated electrodes respectively. The potentials set by the cathodically polarised electrodes are less positive than of the Te/TeO₂ system whereas those set by the anodically polarised electrodes are more positive.

For the sake of comparison, the E' values obtained by extrapolating the $E_{\text{h}}-p_{\text{H}_2}$ plots obtained in air and out of contact with atmospheric oxygen to $p_{\text{H}_2} = 0$ together with the difference from the thermodynamic E' value of the Te/TeO₂ system (0.529 volt) are listed in Table I.

TABLE I

Electrode.	E'_0 in presence of air.	Diff from E'_0 (thermodynamic).	E'_0 out of contact with air.	Diff. from E'_0 (thermodynamic)
Deposited from neutral tellurate	650 mv	+120 mv		
Deposited from alkaline tellurate	680	+150		
Deposited from acid tellurite			530 mv (vacuum)	...
			440 (hydrogen)	-90 mv
			600 (nitrogen)	+70
Powdered	530 (p_H 1.5)	...	530 (p_H 2.9)	...
	570 (p_H 7.11)	+40		
Sublimed			530	...
	530 (p_H 1.5)	...	500 (hydrogen)	-30
Massive	600 (p_H 7.12)	+160	400 (cathodic polarisation)	-130
			650 (anodic polarisation)	-120

DISCUSSION

Tellurium is known to afford the oxides TeO_2 and TeO_3 . No thermodynamic values are known for the oxide TeO_3 , hence we shall limit our discussion to the dioxide. According to Latimer (*loc. cit.*) the thermodynamic E'_0 value of the Te/TeO_2 system, as calculated from the free energy change of the reaction:

amounts to 0.529 volt at 25°.

Comparison of the E'_0 values in Table I with the thermodynamic one indicates that values approaching the latter are obtained only in case where the electrodes are subjected to the alternate action of hydrogen and high vacuum and when the measurements are taken out of contact with atmospheric oxygen. Under these conditions the electrode behaves as a tellurium-tellurium dioxide electrode. Similar behaviour was observed in the case of electrodes prepared from the powdered metal within the p_H range (1.5) for the potentials set 3 hours after immersion and all over the p_H range after prolonged immersion (24 hours). In presence of air and when the massive electrodes are used, on the other hand, potentials more positive than the thermodynamic ones are obtained. This behaviour is similar to that previously observed by Tourky and Moussa in the case of arsenic and antimony and is most probably due to an oxygen-overvoltage effect (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 750; 1949, 1297) superimposing the reversible behaviour of the Te/TeO_2 couple. The overvoltage effect results from the presence on the electrode surface of an oxygen film, most probably in the form of doublets. This film is removed by subjecting the electrode to the alternate action of hydrogen and high vacuum, leading to the attainment of the reversible potentials. This view is further substantiated by the behaviour of the powdered electrodes (Tourky *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) and by the effect of the prevailing gaseous atmosphere on the electrode behaviour. On bubbling nitrogen

gas through the solution in which the electrode is immersed, oxygen is removed from the solution and partly from the electrode surface, leading to potentials less positive than the values obtained in air. In case of hydrogen, the gas may be adsorbed at the electrode surface leading to potentials, less positive than the thermodynamic values. The same behaviour is observed on subjecting the electrode to cathodic polarisation.

The origin of the oxygen-overvoltage effect may be explained in the following manner: In tellurium dioxide, like other polyvalent metal oxides, the lattice defects are restricted to oxygen ions (Mott, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1940, **36**, 472). During the oxidation of the metal, thickening of the oxide is not liable to take place. This is because the metal ions are unable to migrate from the metal surface to the oxide gas interface and the oxygen deposited on the electrode surface will remain as oxygen doublets, subjecting the electrode to an oxygen-overvoltage effect.

Based on the findings of Bowden (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1929, **A125**, 445), the oxygen-overvoltage effect superimposing reversible potential of the Te/TeO_2 system and amounting in maximum to 160 mv is sufficient to cover $2/15$ of the electrode surface with oxygen doublets. Bowden (*loc.cit.*) found that the quantity of electricity necessary to establish oxygen overvoltage per 100 mv was 11×10^{-6} coulombs. Taking the real area equal to 2.3 times the apparent one, he calculated that this quantity of electricity was sufficient to cover $1/15$ of the surface with oxygen doublets. This overvoltage effect was observed in cases of molybdenum and chromium electrodes which exhibited greater tendencies for passivity (Tourky, Issa and Khalifa, *J. Inst. Egypte*, 1956; Issa and Khalifa, this *Journal*, 1956, **33**, 465). In the case of the latter two metals the overvoltage effect was said to be due to the fact that $1/4$ and $2/3$ of the surface are covered with oxygen doublets respectively.

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